

1 **The Fatty Acid Composition of Virgin Olive Oil from Different Cultivars is Determinant for Foam**
2 **Cell Formation by Macrophages**

3
4 *Short Title: Fatty acid EVOO and Foam Cell Formation*
5

6 Angélica Quintero-Flórez¹, Laura Sinausia Nieva², Araceli Sánchez-Ortíz¹, Gabriel Beltrán¹, Javier S.
7 Perona².

8 ¹IFAPA Centro Venta del Llano, Cart. N-323a Km 18, 23620, Mengibar, Spain.

9 ²Instituto de la Grasa, Campus Universidad Pablo de Olavide, Building 46, Ctra. Utrera km 1, 41013
10 Seville, Spain.

11

12 Corresponding author:

13 Angélica Quintero-Flórez

14 IFAPA Centro Venta del Llano

15 Full address: Cart. N-323a Km 18. C.P.: 23620. Mengibar, Spain

16 Phone: (34) 671532221

17 Email: angelica.quintero@juntadeandalucia.es

18

19 **Abstract.**

20 Although the beneficial role of EVOO in the Mediterranean Diet is well-known, its effects on health
21 cannot be attributed solely to oleic acid. In addition to minor components, the presence of other fatty acids
22 (FA), which depend largely on the cultivar among other factors, need to be considered. In the present
23 study, we examined the effect of chylomicron remnant-like particles (CRLP) enriched in fatty acids of
24 virgin olive oil (EVOO) from 'Chetoui', 'Buidiego', 'Galega', 'Blanqueta' and 'Picual' cultivars on the
25 foam cell formation by THP-1 macrophages. THP-1 cells were incubated with EVOO-CRLP for 24h.
26 Lipid accumulation in cells was measured by determining intracellular total triacylglycerol (TAG)
27 concentration and FA composition. Intracellular TAG concentrations were higher in cells incubated with
28 'Chetoui' and 'Blanqueta' CRLP (0.33 ± 0.05 and 0.38 ± 0.07 $\mu\text{mol}/\text{mg}$ of protein respectively) than with
29 'Buidiego' and 'Picual' CRLP (0.20 ± 0.05 and 0.24 ± 0.06 $\mu\text{mol}/\text{mg}$ of protein respectively). In
30 conclusion, linoleic acid-rich EVOO induced higher TAG incorporation into THP-1 macrophages
31 compared to oleic acid-rich EVOO, being the 18:1/18:2 ratio consistently correlated with intracellular
32 TAG accumulation. The results of this study demonstrated that the differences in EVOO-FA composition
33 may have an important role on foam cell formation.

34 **Keywords.** Extra Virgin Olive Oil; fatty acids; lipid; macrophages; foam cells

35 INTRODUCTION

36 Virgin olive oil (VOO) is the primary source of fat in the Mediterranean diet, but it is appreciated
37 worldwide because of its nutritional benefits¹. The consumption of olive oil has been associated with
38 many desirable nutritional properties including lower incidence of coronary heart disease and cancer².

39 VOO is defined as: “oil- obtained from the fruit of the olive tree solely by mechanical or other
40 physical means under conditions, particularly thermal conditions, that do not lead to alterations in the oil,
41 and which have not undergone any treatment other than washing, decantation, centrifugation and
42 filtration”³. Extra Virgin Olive Oil (EVOO) is a quality category involves the lower limits for quality
43 parameters established by the International Olive Council and the absence of any sensory defects³.

44 The composition of EVOO is primarily triacylglycerols (TAG) (~99%) and secondarily free fatty
45 acids (FA), mono- and diacylglycerols, and an array other lipophilic compounds, such as hydrocarbons,
46 sterols, aliphatic alcohols, tocopherols, and pigments. FA present in olive oil are principally palmitic
47 (C16:0), palmitoleic (C16:1), stearic (C18:0), oleic (C18:1), linoleic (C18:2), and linolenic (C18:3) acids.
48 Myristic (C14:0), heptadecanoic (17:0) and eicosanoic acids (20.0) are found at trace amounts.
49 Nevertheless, the FA composition of EVOO may differ, depending on the zone of production, the latitude,
50 the climate, the olive cultivar, and fruit ripening stage⁴⁻⁶.

51 One of the most important factors affecting the FA composition of EVOO is the cultivar, although it
52 is rarely mentioned in nutritional studies^{7,8}. Different authors reported that the FA composition of EVOO
53 shows a strong cultivar component, which explains over 70% of the variability found, especially palmitic,
54 stearic, oleic and linoleic acids. Therefore, the FA composition of EVOO may differ substantially, ranging
55 from 75% of oleic and < 5% linoleic acid in the ‘Picual’ oils to 55% of oleic acid and 20% of linoleic acid
56 for the ‘Blanqueta’ cultivar⁹. These remarkable differences might have relevant effects in the healthy
57 properties that have been attributed to EVOO.

58 There a wide agreement about the beneficial effects of EVOO associated with the oleic acid
59 content¹, including the protection against oxidative stress, blood pressure lowering, reduction of total and
60 LDL-cholesterol levels and even the reduction of the risk of breast, prostate and colorectal cancer. In

61 addition, oleic acid has been regarded as responsible for beneficial effects also in the postprandial state^{10,11}
62 and the first events occurring during the progression of atherogenesis, when forming part of chylomicrons
63 (CM)¹².

64 Dietary lipid components are absorbed by enterocytes and carried in CM, which are large TAG-rich
65 lipoproteins (TRL) secreted into lymph and pass into the blood via thoracic duct. CM undergo rapid
66 lipolysis by lipoprotein lipase (LPL), a process that removes some of their TAG and forms smaller CM
67 remnants (CMR), which deliver the remaining TAG, cholesterol and other lipids to the liver^{13,14}. It has
68 been demonstrated as CMR can cross the endothelial barrier and enter into the arterial wall^{15,16}. CMR have
69 also been shown to induce foam cell formation in a variety of macrophage populations,
70 including those derived from the human monocyte cell line THP-1¹⁷⁻¹⁹, and furthermore, without need of
71 further oxidation²⁰.

72 The FA composition of CMR influences their uptake and lipid accumulation in macrophages^{12,21}.
73 De Pascale et al.¹² studied the effects of CMR-like particles (CRLP) enriched in saturated fatty acids
74 (SFA), monounsaturated fatty acids (MUFA), n-6 polyunsaturated fatty acids (PUFA) and n-3 PUFA,
75 obtained by incorporating TAG from palm, olive, corn and fish oil, respectively, on THP-1 macrophage
76 foam cell formation. They reported that CRLP enriched in SFA or MUFAs were taken up more rapidly
77 than those enriched in n-6 or n-3 PUFA and that SFA-rich particles showed the greatest lipid
78 accumulation.

79 Accordingly, the FA composition of CMR may be determinant for the accumulation of cholesterol
80 and TAG in the macrophages, affecting their metabolism and modulating their atherogenicity^{19,22}.
81 However, the effect of different FA profiles of monovarietal oils on foam cell formation from
82 macrophages has not been addressed so far. Therefore, in the present study we investigated the effect of
83 fatty acid composition of EVOO from five olive cultivars on foam cell formation by THP-1 macrophages.

84 MATERIALS AND METHODS

85 Chemicals

86 Cholesterol and cholesteryl esters (CE) were supplied by Larodan Inc. (Malmö, Sweden).
87 Phospholipids (PL) (phosphatidylcholine, lysophosphatidylcholine, phosphatidylethanolamine,
88 phosphatidylinositol, phosphatidylserine and sphingomyelin), Trypan Blue, albumin (BSA) and Oil red O
89 were obtain from Sigma-Aldrich (St Louis, MO, USA). Human serum was supplied by VWR International
90 Eurolab, S.L (Spain). The THP-1 monocyte-macrophage cell line was provided by the European
91 Collection of Cell Cultures, (ECACC, UK). RPMI 1640 medium with L-Glutamine (L-alanyl-glutamine)
92 and fetal bovine serum (FBS) were purchased from Biowest SAS (France). Penicillin-Streptomycin (5000
93 U/mL) was obtained from Gibco (Paisley, UK). Phorbol 12-myristate 13-acetate (PMA) and phosphate
94 buffered saline (PBS) was supplied by Fisher Scientific (US). All other chemicals were analytical reagent
95 grade.

96 Plant Material and virgin olive oil extraction

97 'Picual', 'Buidiego', 'Blanqueta', 'Galega' and 'Chetoui' Olive (*O. europaea*, L.) olive cultivars
98 were selected according to differences in their FA composition. The trees were spaced 7 x 7 m and grown
99 in the experimental orchard of Centro IFAPA 'Venta Del Llano'- Mengibar, Jaen (Spain) using standard
100 growing techniques. The study was carried out during the 2013/14 crop year. Olives were harvested
101 separately from two olive trees per cultivar.

102 EVOO extraction was performed using an Abencor laboratory oil mill (Comercial Abengoa, S.A.,
103 Seville, Spain) equipped with a hammer mill, a thermobeater and a paste centrifuge; it simulates at
104 laboratory scale the industrial process of EVOO production. The extraction was carried out for each
105 cultivar and tree separately. The milling of olive fruits was performed using a stainless steel hammer mill
106 operating at 3000 rpm provided with a 5 mm sieve. The olive paste malaxation was carried out at 28 °C
107 with kneading at 50 rpm for 45 min. Centrifugation of the kneaded olive paste was performed in a basket

108 centrifuge at 3500 rpm for 1 min. After centrifugation, the obtained oil was decanted, filtered and stored in
109 glass bottles at -20 °C in the dark without headspace and under N₂ until analysis.

110 **Fatty Acid Composition of virgin olive oil**

111 Fatty acid methyl esters (FAME) were prepared as described by the EU regulation 2568/91²³. The
112 chromatographic separation was carried out on a Perkin–Elmer Autosystem gas chromatograph (Perkin–
113 Elmer, Spain) equipped with an autosampler, split/splitless injector, flame ionization detector (FID) and a
114 fused silica capillary BPX70 column of 50 m length x 0.25 mm i.d. and 0.25 µm of film thickness (SGE
115 Scientific PTY Ltd., Australia). Helium was used as carrier gas and the oven temperature was maintained
116 at 198°C throughout the analysis. The injector and detector temperatures were 235 and 245°C,
117 respectively. The results were expressed as relative area percent of the total.

118 **Preparation of chylomicron remnant-like particles (CRLP)**

119 TAG were isolated from ‘Chetoui’, ‘Buidiego’, ‘Galega’, ‘Blanqueta’ and ‘Picual’ EVOO by
120 solid-phase extraction (SPE) using diol cartridges (Superclean LC-Diol; Supelco, Bellefonte, PA) and
121 hexane:methylene chloride (9:1, v/v) as eluent. The eluate containing TAG was evaporated to dryness
122 under a stream of nitrogen and re-dissolved in hexane. CRLP were prepared using a lipid mixture
123 containing 70% TAG from EVOO, 2% cholesterol, 3% cholesteryl esters (CE) and 25% PL as described
124 previously²⁴. The composition of the initial PL moieties was: phosphatidylcholine 70.50%,
125 lysophosphatidylcholine 6.88%, phosphatidylethanolamine 11.00%, phosphatidylinositol 2.58%,
126 phosphatidylserine 2.58% and sphingomyelin 6.54%.

127 Lipids were sonicated by immersing a clean ultrasonic probe (Bandelin Electronics, Berlin,
128 Germany) directly into the lipid mixture in 0.9% NaCl in tricine buffer (20 mM, pH 7.4), and supplying
129 the probe with 50W for 20 min (5-min bursts with 5-min rest periods to allow for cooling) at 56°C. The
130 resulting emulsion was brought to a density of 1.21 g/mL with KBr, layered under a stepwise density
131 gradient (2.5 mL, d=1.065 g/mL; 2.5 mL, d=1.020 g/mL; 3 mL, d=1.006 g/mL) as described previously²⁴,
132 and centrifuged at 17 000g for 20 min at 20 °C (Beckman Optima L-90K centrifuge; Beckman Coulter,

133 Palo Alto, CA) in a SW41Ti swing-out rotor. The upper layer, which was an uneven emulsion of lipids,
134 was discarded. The removed layer was replaced with an equal volume of NaCl solution (d=1.006 g/mL),
135 and tubes were centrifuged at 70 000g for 1 h (20 °C) in a SW41Ti swing-out rotor. The upper layer was
136 then collected and stored at 4 °C until use (max 2 days).

137 **Apolipoprotein E transfer to CRLP**

138 The apolipoprotein transfer was achieved by incubation of the lipid emulsion with a fraction of
139 human serum (1:2, vol/vol), prepared by ultracentrifugation and dialyzed before use²⁴ (5 h, 4°C). After
140 incubation, the particles were ultracentrifuged (154 000 g, 16 h, 12°C) under a NaCl solution (d=1.006
141 g/mL). The upper layer was collected and recentrifuged (254 000g, 5 h, 12°C) under a NaCl solution
142 (d=1.006 g/mL) to isolate the CRLP fraction. CRLP were dialyzed before use (2h, 4°C) and stored a 4°C.
143 All preparations were used within one week.

144 **Culture of THP-1 macrophages**

145 THP-1 monocytes were maintained in suspension at a density of (3-8)x10⁵ cell/mL in RPMI 1640
146 culture medium containing 10% fetal bovine serum (previously inactivated at 56°C, 30 min), 2 mM L-
147 alanil-glutamine, 100 U/mL-1 penicillin and 100 ug/mL streptomycin at 37°C in 95% air/5% CO₂.

148 The cells at a 1 x 10⁶/mL concentration were induced to differentiate into macrophages by
149 incubation with phorbol myristate acetate (PMA) (200 ng/mL) for 72 h at 37°C in 95% air/5% CO₂. After
150 this time, the cells adhering to the culture dishes were washed with RPMI 1640 culture medium without
151 FBS (3 x 2 mL) to remove any undifferentiated cells and traces of PMA. The viability of the THP-1
152 monocytes, as assessed by Trypan blue exclusion, was >90% in all experiments. The adherent cell was 70-
153 80%, and cell viability was unaffected with incubation with CRLPs.

154 **Lipid accumulation studies**

155 Cells adhering to the culture dishes were added 2 mL RPMI 1640 culture medium without fetal
156 bovine serum and were incubated with CRLP (0.15 μmol TAG/mL of medium) for 24 h at 37°C in 95%

157 air/5% CO₂. For Oil Red O staining, cells were washed with PBS 1X (3 x 2 mL) and 60% propan-2-ol,
158 then 1 mL of Oil red O (0.15% w/v) in 40% propan-2-ol/H₂O v/v was added. After 10 min, the stain was
159 removed and cells were washed with 3 mL of PBS 1X as many times as necessary to remove traces of the
160 solution. Then, 2 mL of glycerol (30%) were added and images were captured using a microscope-
161 mounted Canon digital camera.

162 For intracellular lipid analysis, cells were washed with PBS (3 x 3 mL), harvested in 0.7 μL PBS,
163 and kept on a bed of ice. Cells were then disrupted by sonication for 5 s (x 2, 50 W), and a sample was
164 taken for protein determination (preserved at -70°C) and the rest were kept at -20°C for subsequent total
165 TAG determination and FA composition.

166 **Triacylglycerol and fatty acid composition**

167 Total TAG in CRLP and cells were determined by enzymatic analysis using a commercial
168 enzymatic reagent colorimetric/fluorimetric kit (BioVision Incorporated, USA). For the determination of
169 CRLP FA composition, TAG were isolated by SPE diol columns as described above and were
170 transmethylated using sodium metoxide in methanol (0.5%). For the analysis of FA composition in the
171 cells, intracellular TAG were directly transmethylated using a metilation mixture (MeOH-toluene-DMP-
172 H₂SO₄) and heptane. The resulting FAME of CRLP and cells were analyzed by GC, using a model 5890
173 series II GC (Hewlett-Packard Co, Avondale, AZ) equipped with a flame ionization detector and a capillary
174 silica column Supelcowax 10 (Supelco, Co, Bellefonte, PA) of 60 m length and 0.25 mm internal diameter.
175 FAME were identified by the comparison of their retention times against those of standards and quantified
176 by external standard using peak area integration; results were expressed as relative area percentage. CRLP
177 and cell protein content was measured by the method of Bradford using BSA as standard.

178 **Statistical analysis**

179 Results are expressed as means \pm SD, unless otherwise stated. Statistical analyses were conducted
180 using the GraphPad Prism v.5 statistical package (GraphPad Software, Inc.). Statistical significance was
181 assessed by one-way or two-way ANOVA, followed by Bonferroni's multiple comparison tests.

182 Correlations between variables were assessed using Pearson's correlation coefficients. Differences were
183 considered statistically significant at $p < 0.05$.

184 **RESULTS**

185 **Chylomicron remnant-like particle TAG content and fatty acid composition**

186 The TAG content was similar in all five types of CRLP ($\mu\text{mol} / \text{mL}$, $n=3$): 'Chetoui' CRLP, $2.38 \pm$
187 0.4 ; 'Buidiego' CRLP, 1.99 ± 0.62 ; 'Galega' CRLP, 2.76 ± 0.17 ; 'Blanqueta' CRLP, 1.93 ± 0.10 ; 'Picual'
188 CRLP, 1.83 ± 0.53 .

189 Overall, the FA profile CRLP-TAG and EVOO of all cultivars studies was similar (**Table 1**).
190 However, significant differences were observed among cultivars, which resulted in differences in CRLP-
191 TAG. Oleic acid content was the main FA in all CRLP, accounting for 60-76% of all FA, with significant
192 differences among cultivars. Likewise, linoleic acid ranged from 4 to 18%. 'Picual' CRLP showed the
193 highest oleic acid content (76.6%) and the lowest linoleic acid content (4.1%), whereas 'Chetoui' CRPL
194 had the lowest oleic acid content (60.9%) and the greatest linoleic acid content (18.9%). As a
195 consequence, the MUFA concentration was highest in 'Picual' CRLP and PUFA concentration in
196 'Chetoui' CRLP. SFA content was higher in 'Blanqueta' CRLP.

197 **Intracellular lipid accumulation in THP-1 macrophages**

198 THP-1 macrophages were treated with 'Chetoui', 'Buidiego', 'Galega', 'Blanqueta' and 'Picual'
199 CRLP ($0.15 \mu\text{mol TAG/mL}$) for 24 h. Incubation of macrophages with all CRLP resulted in increased
200 intracellular accumulation of lipids as assessed by Oil Red O staining (**Figure 1**). Images revealed a light
201 staining in control cells and a strong red staining in cells incubated with CRLP, confirming the
202 intracellular lipid incorporation.

203 Intracellular TAG concentrations differed according to the type of CRLP used. There was a
204 significantly higher accumulation of TAG in cells incubated with 'Chetoui' and 'Blanqueta' CRLP than
205 with 'Buidiego' and 'Picual' CRLP (**Figure 2**).

206 The TAG fraction of THP-1 macrophages showed significant differences for the main FA, namely
207 palmitic, palmitoleic, stearic, oleic, linoleic and arachidonic (20:4 n-6) acids and, therefore, for the SFA,
208 MUFA and PUFA contents (**Table 2**). Control cells presented a higher SFA proportion compared with
209 cells incubated with CRLP. Among cells incubated with CRLP, SFA accumulation was enhanced in cells
210 incubated with 'Galega' CRLP (29%), while MUFA concentration was higher in those incubated with
211 'Picual' (62%) and 'Buidiego' (61%) CRLP and lower with 'Chetoui' CRLP (51%). Finally, PUFA
212 content was increased in cells treated with 'Chetoui' CRLP (22%) and decreased with 'Picual' CRLP
213 (11%). As well as in CRLP, palmitic, stearic, oleic and linoleic acids were found with the highest
214 proportions in the intracellular TAG fraction. It was observed that oils with the greatest oleic and linoleic
215 acid contents, led to cells engorged with TAG rich in those FA. Oleic acid was found at higher
216 concentration in cells incubated with 'Picual' CRLP (59%) and whereas the lowest in those treated with
217 'Chetoui' (48%) and 'Galega' CRLP (50%). Conversely, linoleic acid was found at greater amounts in
218 cells incubated with 'Chetoui' CRLP (13%) and at lower concentration in cells incubated with 'Picual'
219 CRLP (4%).

220 The oleic acid to linoleic acid ratio (18:1/18:2 ratio) of the EVOO was plotted against TAG
221 accumulation in cells in order to determine the relationship between oleic and linoleic acid content in the
222 parent oils and lipid intracellular accumulation (**Figure 3A**) and the FA composition in intracellular TAG
223 (**Figure 3B**). A higher 18:1/18:2 ratio was associated with lower TG accumulation in the cells, and very
224 strongly with the intracellular 18:1/18:2 ratio.

225 **DISCUSSION**

226 Dietary fats enter the blood as CM that undergo lipolysis in extra-hepatic capillary beds. The
227 resulting CMR particles contain about 30% of TAG and most cholesterol mass of the parent lipoproteins
228 and are considered atherogenic lipoproteins. CMR are taken by several types of macrophages¹³ and give
229 rise to foam cells by inducing accumulation of cholesterol, TAG or both^{12,13,17,25-27}.

230 A number of epidemiologic studies developed in different countries constitute a firm and reliable
231 experimental base supporting the beneficial effects of the Mediterranean diet, rich in olive oil, with regard
232 to the reduction of cardiovascular disease^{28,29}. Although the benefits of EVOO against cardiovascular
233 disease cannot be attributed solely to oleic acid³⁰, the protective effects have been ascribed to higher
234 intakes of oleic and α -linolenic acid (18:3, n-3) acids and lower intakes of SFA and linoleic acid (18:2, n-
235 6)³¹⁻³⁴.

236 The FA composition of EVOO depends on the zone of production, the latitude, the climate, the
237 variety, and the stage of maturity of the fruit^{4,6}. For instance, Greek, Italian, and Spanish EVOO are, in
238 general terms, low in linoleic and palmitic acids and they have a high percentage of oleic acid. In contrast,
239 Tunisian EVOOs are high in linoleic and palmitic acids and lower in oleic acid⁴. Given these differences,
240 we evaluated the uptake of CRLP prepared with TAG obtained from five EVOO cultivars and the
241 induction of lipid accumulation in macrophages derived from the human monocyte cell line THP-1. Since
242 it is difficult to obtain CMR uncontaminated with lipoproteins of a similar density, such as CM and very-
243 low-density lipoproteins, from human blood, we used CRLP as experimental model²⁴, CRLP have been
244 used by a number authors before to study lipid metabolism^{12,26,35-38}. As their composition can be easily
245 manipulated, providing a suitable and convenient model.

246 We obtained EVOO from 'Chetoui', 'Buidiego', 'Galega', 'Blanqueta' and 'Picual' cultivars,
247 which presented differences in their FA composition and we used their TAG to prepare CRLP that did not
248 differ in their TAG content and whose FA composition was similar to the parent oils (**Table 1**). These
249 findings are consistent with previous works using palm, olive, corn or fish oils^{37,38}.

250 The exposure of human THP-1 cells to EVOO-CRLP caused intracellular lipid accumulation, and
251 thus provided evidence of CRLP uptake by macrophages and foam cell formation. It has been reported
252 that not all CMR are equally taken up by macrophages and the particle size and lipid composition may
253 have a significant influence on the process of uptake and lipid accumulation³⁹. Batt et al¹⁷ studied the
254 effect of LDL and CRLP on lipid accumulation in human monocyte-derived macrophages (HMDMs) and
255 in THP-1 cells. They found that CRLP, without prior oxidation, caused lipid accumulation in human

256 macrophages to an extent comparable to that caused by oxidized LDL. They also reported a greater
257 proportion lipid accumulation in response to CRLP in the form of TAG and in the form of CE in response
258 to oxidized LDL.

259 Our experiments showed that 'Blanqueta' and 'Chetoui' CRLP caused the greatest TAG
260 accumulation in THP-1 cells. 'Blanqueta' CRLP were characterized by higher SFA content and 'Chetoui'
261 CRLP by higher linoleic acid and PUFA content. This result can be comparable with previous works by
262 De Pascale et al.,¹² and Song et al.,²⁷ who added SFA, MUFA and n-6 or n-3 PUFA to THP-1
263 macrophages in the form of CRLP or non-esterified FA, respectively. Both confirmed that SFA are taken
264 up more rapidly and result in greater lipid accumulation in cells, although they observed that PUFA-rich
265 particles caused the lowest lipid accumulation. In contrast, our results showed as the CRLP with greater
266 PUFA content caused more lipid accumulation in cells than MUFA rich-CRLP. In this sense Song et al.²⁷
267 described differences between incubation with oleic or linoleic acids only for cholesterol and not for TAG.
268 Likewise, De Pascale et al.,¹² employed CRLP, reporting significant differences in intracellular TAG
269 accumulation only between palm-CRLP and corn-CRLP although differences between corn-CRLP and
270 olive-CRLP were not observed. Interestingly, in that study the 18:1/18:2 ratio in CRLP (7.65) was similar
271 to that obtained when we prepared CRLP from the 'Buidiego' cultivar (9.63), which caused the lowest
272 TAG accumulation in the cells.

273 When the FA composition of intracellular TAG was compared with that of CRLP, we observed that
274 it was highly preserved, i.e. cells treated with CRLP with the highest concentrations of 18:1, 18:2 or 16:0
275 also exhibited the highest levels of these FA intracellularly. In fact, the 18:1/18:2 ratio in the oils
276 correlated positively and very strongly with the same ratio in cell TAG. Also, we found that 18:1/18:2
277 ratio also correlated with TAG concentration in the cells, although a negative relationship was obtained.
278 Napolitano et al.⁴⁰ studied the influence of the TAG source (trilinolein or triolein) in CRLP in human
279 macrophages. Their results were in close agreement with ours, finding that particles enriched with both
280 trilinolein or triolein, induced a pattern of increase in intracellular TAG synthesis, but that was higher after
281 incubation with trilinolein. However, an important point to consider is that despite all the CRLP employed

282 here were rich in oleic acid, they differed in every other minor FA. Slight differences in the FA can lead to
283 a highly different TAG molecular species composition, which may have important effects in the metabolic
284 fate of lipoproteins, as observed in elderly individuals⁴¹.

285 Although the mechanisms by which TRL are taken up by macrophages have not been studied
286 extensively, CMR are believed to be incorporated into macrophages by two main pathways: uptake of
287 whole particles via membrane receptors and hydrolysis by macrophage-secreted LPL⁴⁰. Extracellular
288 lipolysis seems particularly important for internalization of dietary fatty acids⁴⁰. It has been suggested that
289 Vmax of LPL in the adipose tissue decreases with increasing chain length and unsaturation degree of
290 monoacid CM-TAG due to decreased fluidity of the particle⁴². However, differences between oleic and
291 linoleic-acid rich seem to be significant only for large CM and not for VLDL⁴³. On the other hand, studies
292 carried out in THP-1 cells have proposed that oleic acid-rich dietary fats may prevent excessive lipid
293 accumulation in monocyte/macrophage cells by down-regulating the gene expression of apolipoprotein
294 B48 receptor⁴⁴ and that linoleic acid stimulates CD36 receptor, promoting intracellular TAG
295 accumulation⁴⁵.

296 In conclusion, the results of this study demonstrated that the effect of differences in the FA
297 composition of EVOO is similar to the effect caused by the same FA when forming part of other dietary
298 oils. In fact, linoleic acid-rich EVOO induced higher TAG incorporation into THP-1 macrophages
299 compared to oleic acid-rich EVOO, being 18:1/18:2 ratio consistently correlated with intracellular TAG
300 accumulation. In this regard, the ratio between 18:1 and 18:2 could be used as a helpful marker to identify
301 EVOO with possible cardio-protective effects. Since EVOO oleic and linoleic acid composition is
302 cultivar dependent, among other agronomical factors, this marker could be independent of these factors.

303 Although the results presented here may be a starting point to indicate the possibility of selecting
304 VOO cultivars for specific nutritional uses according to their FA composition, it is certainly too early to
305 give recommendations to the population. Apart from the fatty acid composition, there are many other
306 factors to consider that may have direct or indirect influence on health.

307 **Abbreviations Used**

308 CRLP: chylomicron remnant-like particles

309 VOO: Virgin olive oil

310 EVOO: Extra virgin olive oil

311 TAG: triacylglycerols

312 CM: chylomicrons

313 TRL: TAG-rich lipoproteins

314 SFA: saturated fatty acids

315 MUFA: monounsaturated fatty acids

316 PUFA: polyunsaturated fatty acids

317 CE: cholesteryl esters

318 CMR: chylomicrons remnants

319 FA: fatty acid

320 **Acknowledgment.**

321 This work was supported by the project FEDER-P10-AGR6099 of Junta de Andalucía, the grant CAICEM

322 12-79 with Interprofessional del Aceite de Oliva Español and FEDER-INIA RTA 2010-00013-C02-01.

323 **References**

- 324 1. López-Miranda, J.; Pérez-Jiménez, F.; Ros, E.; De Caterina, R.; Badimón, L.; Covas, M. I.; Escrich, E.;
325 Ordovás, J. M.; Soriguer, F.; Abiá, R.; Alarcón de la Lastra, C.; Battino, M.; Corella, D.; Chamorro-
326 Quirós, J.; Delgado-Lista, J.; Giugliano, D.; Esposito, K.; Estruch, R.; Fernandez-Real, J. M.;
327 Gaforio, J. J.; La Vecchia, C.; Lairon, D.; López-Segura, F.; Mata, P.; Menéndez, J. A.; Muriana, F.
328 J.; Osada, J.; Panagiotakos, D. B.; Paniagua, J. A.; Pérez-Martínez, P.; Perona, J.; Peinado, M. A.;
329 Pineda-Priego, M.; Poulsen, H. E.; Quiles, J. L.; Ramírez-Tortosa, M. C.; Ruano, J.; Serra-Majem,
330 L.; Solá, R.; Solanas, M.; Solfrizzi, V.; de la Torre-Fornell, R.; Trichopoulou, A.; Uceda, M.;
331 Villalba-Montoro, J. M.; Villar-Ortiz, J. R.; Visioli, F.; Yiannakouris, N. Olive oil and health:
332 Summary of the II international conference on olive oil and health consensus report, Jaén and
333 Córdoba (Spain) 2008. *Nutr Metab Cardiovasc Dis* **2010**, *20*, 284-294.
- 334 2. Frankel, E. N. Nutritional and Biological Properties of Extra Virgin Olive Oil. *J. Agric. Food Chem.*
335 **2011**, *59*, 785-792.
- 336 3. International Olive Council. Trade Standard Applying to Olive Oils and Olive-Pomace Oils (**February**
337 **2015**). *COI 2015, T.15/NC No 3/REV.8 2015*.
- 338 4. Boskou, D.; Blekas, G.; Tsimidou, M. Olive Oil Composition. In *Olive Oil: Chemistry and Technology*,
339 Second Edition.; Boskou, D., Ed.; AOCS Publishing: Greece, 2006; pp 41-72.
- 340 5. Beltrán, G.; del Río, C.; Sánchez, S.; Martínez, L. Influence of Harvest Date and Crop Yield on the
341 Fatty Acid Composition of Virgin Olive Oils from Cv. Picual. *J. Agric. Food Chem.* **2004**, *52*, 3434-
342 3440.
- 343 6. Mousa, Y.; Gerasopoulos, D.; Metzidakis, I.; Kiritsakis, A. Effect of Altitude on Fruit and Oil Quality
344 Characteristics of 'Mastoides' Olives. *J. Sci. Food Agric.* **1996**, *71*, 345-350.
- 345 7. Kaliora, A. C.; Artemiou, A.; Giogios, I.; Kalogeropoulos, N. The impact of fruit maturation on
346 bioactive microconstituents, inhibition of serum oxidation and inflammatory markers in stimulated
347 PBMCs and sensory characteristics of Koroneiki virgin olive oils from Messenia, Greece. *Food*
348 *Funct.* **2013**, *4*, 1185-1194.

- 349 8. Fabiani, R.; Sepporta, M. V.; Mazza, T.; Rosignoli, P.; Fuccelli, R.; De Bartolomeo, A.; Crescimanno,
350 M.; Taticchi, A.; Esposito, S.; Servili, M.; Morozzi, G. Influence of cultivar and concentration of
351 selected phenolic constituents on the in vitro chemiopreventive potential of olive oil extracts. *J.*
352 *Agric. Food Chem.* **2011**, *59*, 8167-8174.
- 353 9. Uceda, M.; Hermoso, M.; Aguilera, M. P. La Calidad del Aceite de Oliva. In *El cultivo del olivo*,
354 edition 6.; Barranco, D., Ed.; Mundi-Prensa: España, 2008; pp 699-727.
- 355 10. Pérez-Jiménez, F.; López-Miranda, J.; Mata, P. Protective effect of dietary monounsaturated fat on
356 arteriosclerosis: Beyond cholesterol. *Atherosclerosis* **2002**, *163*, 385-398.
- 357 11. Abia, R.; Pacheco, Y. M.; Perona, J. S.; Montero, E.; Muriana, F. J. G.; Ruiz-Gutiérrez, V. The
358 metabolic availability of dietary triacylglycerols from two high oleic oils during the postprandial
359 period does not depend on the amount of oleic acid ingested by healthy men. *J. Nutr.* **2001**, *131*, 59-
360 65.
- 361 12. De Pascale, C.; Avella, M.; Perona, J. S.; Ruiz-Gutierrez, V.; Wheeler-Jones, C. P. D.; Botham, K. M.
362 Fatty acid composition of chylomicron remnant-like particles influences their uptake and induction
363 of lipid accumulation in macrophages. *FEBS J* **2006**, *273*, 5632-5640.
- 364 13. Yu, K. C.; Mamo, J. C. L. Chylomicron-remnant-induced foam cell formation and cytotoxicity: A
365 possible mechanism of cell death in atherosclerosis. *Clin. Sci.* **2000**, *98*, 183-192.
- 366 14. Redgrave, T. G.; Ly, H. I.; Quintao, E. C. R.; Ramberg, C. F.; Boston, R. C. Clearance from plasma of
367 triacylglycerol and cholesteryl ester after intravenous injection of chylomicron-like lipid emulsions in
368 rats and man. *Biochem. J.* **1993**, *290*, 843-847.
- 369 15. Proctor, S. D.; Mamo, J. C. L. Intimal Retention of Cholesterol Derived From Apolipoprotein B100-
370 and Apolipoprotein B48-Containing Lipoproteins in Carotid Arteries of Watanabe Heritable
371 Hyperlipidemic Rabbits. *Arterioscl. Throm. Vas* **2003**, *23*, 1595-1600.
- 372 16. Proctor, S. D.; Vine, D. F.; Mamo, J. C. L. Arterial retention of apolipoprotein B48- and B100-
373 containing lipoproteins in atherogenesis. *Curr. Opin. Lipidol.* **2002**, *13*, 461-470.

- 374 17. Batt, K. V.; Avella, M.; Moore, E. H.; Jackson, B.; Suckling, K. E.; Botham, K. M. Differential effects
375 of low-density lipoprotein and chylomicron remnants on lipid accumulation in human macrophages.
376 *Exp. Biol. Med.* **2004**, *229*, 528-537.
- 377 18. Moore, E. H.; Bejta, F.; Avella, M.; Suckling, K. E.; Botham, K. M. Efflux of lipid from macrophages
378 after induction of lipid accumulation by chylomicron remnants. *BBA-Mol Cell Biol L* **2005**, *1735*, 20-
379 29.
- 380 19. Moore, E. H.; Napolitano, M.; Avella, M.; Bejta, F.; Suckling, K. E.; Bravo, E.; Botham, K. M.
381 Protection of chylomicron remnants from oxidation by incorporation of probucol into the particles
382 enhances their uptake by human macrophages and increases lipid accumulation in the cells. *Eur. J.*
383 *Biochem.* **2004**, *271*, 2417-2427.
- 384 20. Napolitano, M.; Avella, M.; Botham, K. M.; Bravo, E. Chylomicron remnant induction of lipid
385 accumulation in J774 macrophages is associated with up-regulation of triacylglycerol synthesis
386 which is not dependent on oxidation of the particles. *BBA-Mol Cell Biol L* **2003**, *1631*, 255-264.
- 387 21. Hunter, K. A.; Crosbie, L. C.; Horgan, G. W.; Miller, G. J.; Dutta-Roy, A. K. Effect of diets rich in
388 oleic acid, stearic acid and linoleic acid on postprandial haemostatic factors in young healthy men.
389 *Br. J. Nutr.* **2001**, *86*, 207-215.
- 390 22. Cabello-Moruno, R.; Perona, J. S.; Ruiz-Gutierrez, V. Influence of minor components of olive oils on
391 the composition and size of TRLs and on macrophage receptors involved in foam cell formation.
392 *Biochem. Soc. Trans.* **2007**, *35*, 470-471.
- 393 23. European Community Regulation. Characteristics of olive and pomace oils and on their analytical
394 methods. *Off. J. Eur. communities* **1991**, *2568/91*, L248,1-82.
- 395 24. Antelo, A.; Perona, J. S. Evaluation of a method of preparation of lipid emulsions as a model for
396 chylomicron-like particles. *J. Liposome Res.* **2013**, *23*, 126-133.
- 397 25. Botham, K. M.; Bravo, E.; Elliott, J.; Wheeler-Jones, C. P. D. Direct interaction of dietary lipids
398 carried in chylomicron remnants with cells of the artery wall: Implications for atherosclerosis
399 development. *Curr. Pharm. Des.* **2005**, *11*, 3681-3695.

- 400 26. Napolitano, M.; Batt, K. V.; Avella, M.; Bravo, E.; Botham, K. M. Lipid synthesis in macrophages
401 derived from the human cell line THP-1: Modulation of the effects of native and oxidized
402 chylomicronremnant-like particles by oestrogen. *Clin. Sci.* **2001**, *101*, 403-413.
- 403 27. Song, Y.; Zhang, L.; Li, H.; Gu, Y.; Li, F.; Jiang, L.; Liu, F.; Ye, J.; Li, Q. Polyunsaturated fatty acid
404 relatively decreases cholesterol content in THP-1 macrophage-derived foam cell: Partly correlates
405 with expression profile of CIDE and PAT members. *Lipids Health Dis* **2013**, *12*, 111.
- 406 28. Wahrburg, U.; Kratz, M.; Cullen, P. Mediterranean diet, olive oil and health. *Eur. J. Lipid. Sci.*
407 *Technol.* **2002**, *104*, 698-705.
- 408 29. Guasch-Ferré, M.; Hu, F. B.; Martínez-González, M. A.; Fitó, M.; Bulló, M.; Estruch, R.; Ros, E.;
409 Corella, D.; Recondo, J.; Gómez-Gracia, E.; Fiol, M.; Lapetra, J.; Serra-Majem, L.; Muñoz, M. A.;
410 Pintó, X.; Lamuela-Raventós, R. M.; Basora, J.; Buil-Cosiales, P.; Sorlí, J. V.; Ruiz-Gutiérrez, V.;
411 Martínez, J. A.; and Salas-Salvadó, J. Olive oil intake and risk of cardiovascular disease and
412 mortality in the PREDIMED Study. *BMC Med* **2014**, *13*, 12-78.
- 413 30. Perona, J. S.; Cabello-Moruno, R.; Ruiz-Gutierrez, V. The role of virgin olive oil components in the
414 modulation of endothelial function. *J. Nutr. Biochem.* **2006**, *17*, 429-445.
- 415 31. Hu, F. B. The Mediterranean diet and mortality - Olive oil and beyond. *N. Engl. J. Med.* **2003**, *348*,
416 2595-2596.
- 417 32. De Lorgeril, M.; Renaud, S.; Mamelle, N.; Salen, P.; Martin, J. -.; Monjaud, I.; Guidollet, J.; Touboul,
418 P.; Delaye, J. Mediterranean alpha-linolenic acid-rich diet in secondary prevention of coronary heart
419 disease. *Lancet* **1994**, *343*, 1454-1459.
- 420 33. Mensink, R. P.; Katan, M. B. Effect of dietary fatty acids on serum lipids and lipoproteins: A meta-
421 analysis of 27 trials. *Arterioscler. Throm.* **1992**, *12*, 911-919.
- 422 34. Gardner, C. D.; Kraemer, H. C. Monounsaturated versus polyunsaturated dietary fat and serum lipids:
423 A meta-analysis. *Arterioscler. Thromb. Vasc. Biol.* **1995**, *15*, 1917-1927.

- 424 35. Maranhão, R. C.; Feres, M. C.; Martins, M. T.; Mesquita, C. H.; Toffoletto, O.; Vinagre, C. G. C.;
425 Gianinni, S. D.; Pileggi, F. Plasma kinetics of a chylomicron-like emulsion in patients with coronary
426 artery disease. *Atherosclerosis* **1996**, *126*, 15-25.
- 427 36. Bentley, C.; Hathaway, N.; Widdows, J.; Bejta, F.; De Pascale, C.; Avella, M.; Wheeler-Jones, C. P.
428 D.; Botham, K. M.; Lawson, C. Influence of chylomicron remnants on human monocyte activation in
429 vitro. *Nutr Metab Cardiovasc Dis* **2010**, *21*, 871-878.
- 430 37. López-Soldado, I.; Avella, M.; Botham, K. M. Differential influence of different dietary fatty acids on
431 very low-density lipoprotein secretion when delivered to hepatocytes in chylomicron remnants.
432 *Metabolism* **2009**, *58*, 186-195.
- 433 38. Lopez-Soldado, I.; Avella, M.; Botham, K. M. Comparison of the effects of dietary saturated, mono-
434 unsaturated and polyunsaturated fatty acids on very-low-density lipoprotein secretion when delivered
435 to hepatocytes in chylomicron remnant-like particles. *Biochem. Soc. Trans.* **2007**, *35*, 440-441.
- 436 39. Botham, K. M.; Wheeler-Jones, C. P. D. Postprandial lipoproteins and the molecular regulation of
437 vascular homeostasis. *Progr Lipid Res* **2013**, *52*, 446-464.
- 438 40. Napolitano, M.; Bravo, E. Evidence of dual pathways for lipid uptake during chylomicron remnant-
439 like particle processing by human macrophages. *J. Vasc. Res.* **2006**, *43*, 355-366.
- 440 41. Perona, J. S.; Cañizares, J.; Montero, E.; Sánchez-Domínguez, J. M.; Pacheco, Y. M.; Ruiz-Gutierrez,
441 V. Dietary virgin olive oil triacylglycerols as an independent determinant of very low-density
442 lipoprotein composition. *Nutrition* **2004**, *20*, 509-514.
- 443 42. Sato K; Takahashi T FAU - Takahashi, Y.; Takahashi Y FAU - Shiono, H.; Shiono H FAU - Katoh, N.;
444 Katoh N FAU - Akiba, Y.; Akiba Y Preparation of chylomicrons and VLDL with monoacid-rich
445 triacylglycerol and characterization of kinetic parameters in lipoprotein lipase-mediated hydrolysis in
446 chickens. *J Nutr* **1999**, *129*, 126-131.
- 447 43. Sato, K.; Takahashi, Y.; Takahashi, T.; Katoh, N.; Akiba, Y. Identification of factors regulating
448 lipoprotein lipase catalyzed hydrolysis in rats with the aid of monoacid-rich lipoprotein preparations
449 (1). *J. Nutr. Biochem.* **2002**, *13*, 528-538.

- 450 44. Varela, L. M.; Ortega-Gomez, A.; Lopez, S.; Abia, R.; Muriana, F. J. G.; Bermudez, B. The effects of
451 dietary fatty acids on the postprandial triglyceride-rich lipoprotein/apoB48 receptor axis in human
452 monocyte/macrophage cells. *J. Nutr. Biochem.* **2013**, *24*, 2031-2039.
- 453 45. Vallvé, J.; Uliaque, K.; Girona, J.; Cabré, A.; Ribalta, J.; Heras, M.; Masana, L. Unsaturated fatty
454 acids and their oxidation products stimulate CD36 gene expression in human macrophages.
455 *Atherosclerosis* **2002**, *164*, 45-56.

456 **Figure Captions**

457 **Figure 1.** Lipid accumulation in Cells THP-1 macrophages incubated with CRLPs containing TAG from
458 'Chetoui', 'Buidiego', 'Galega', 'Blanqueta' and 'Picual' EVOO cultivars. THP-1 macrophages were
459 incubated with CRLPs (final concentration 0.15 $\mu\text{mol TAG/mL}$) for 24 h and stained with Oil Red O.

460 **Figure 2.** Total TAG accumulated after 24 h in THP-1 macrophagus incubated with 'Chetoui',
461 'Buidiego', 'Galega', 'Blanqueta' and 'Picual' CRLPs. Data are the mean from three separate
462 experiments, and error bars show the SD. Different letters indicate significant difference ($p < 0.05$) by
463 one-way ANOVA analysis and Bonferroni's post-hoc test.

464 **Figure 3.** Correlation of oleic acid to linoleic acid ratio (18:1/18:2) of EVOO with (A) TAG accumulated
465 in THP-1 macrophages and (B) oleic acid to linoleic acid ratio (18:1/18:2) in intracellular THP-1
466 macrophages after incubation with 'Chetoui', 'Buidiego', 'Galega', 'Blanqueta' and 'Picual' CRLPs.

Table 1. Fatty Acid composition of EVOO from 'Chetoui', 'Buidiego', 'Galega', 'Blanqueta' and 'Picual' cultivars, and of TAG in CRLP which were prepared using the TAG from the same oils. .

	'CHETOU'		'BUIDIEGO'		'GALEGA'		'BLANQUETA'		'PICUAL'	
	EVOO	CRLP	EVOO	CRLP	EVOO	CRLP	EVOO	CRLP	EVOO	CRLP
16:0	13.5 ± 0.05	13.8 ± 0.22 a	13.4 ± 0.10	13.8 ± 0.3 a	15.8 ± 0.21	15.3 ± 0.30 b	16.4 ± 0.21	16.6 ± 1.20 c	12.3 ± 0.04	12.5 ± 0.46 d
16:1	0.37 ± 0.01	0.76 ± 0.05 a	0.71 ± 0.02	1.36 ± 0.23 a,b	2.13 ± 0.03	2.62 ± 0.05 b	1.39 ± 0.05	1.40 ± 0.78 a,b	1.01 ± 0.02	1.37 ± 0.10 a,b
17:0	0.05 ± 0.01	0.07 ± 0.02	0.06 ± 0.01	0.11 ± 0.04	0.11 ± 0.01	0.15 ± 0.04	0.12 ± 0.01	0.14 ± 0.10	0.03 ± 0.01	0.07 ± 0.03
17:1	0.08 ± 0.01	0.10 ± 0.02	0.07 ± 0.01	0.25 ± 0.24	0.26 ± 0.01	0.28 ± 0.02	0.25 ± 0.02	0.14 ± 0.16	0.07 ± 0.02	0.14 ± 0.04
18:0	2.55 ± 0.02	3.52 ± 0.15 a,b	2.87 ± 0.02	4.12 ± 0.83 a	1.83 ± 0.01	2.46 ± 0.24 b	2.11 ± 0.03	2.80 ± 0.26 b	2.56 ± 0.02	3.44 ± 0.22 a,b
18:1	62.5 ± 0.08	60.9 ± 0.17 a	75.4 ± 0.19	70.6 ± 1.24 b	74.6 ± 0.23	71.7 ± 0.60 c	64.1 ± 0.23	62.9 ± 0.63 d	79.9 ± 0.06	76.6 ± 1.28 e
18:2	19.7 ± 0.01	18.9 ± 0.19 a	6.22 ± 0.04	7.33 ± 1.25 b	4.29 ± 0.02	5.69 ± 0.45 c	14.3 ± 0.01	14.3 ± 0.29 d	3.06 ± 0.03	4.11 ± 0.56 e
18:3	0.55 ± 0.04	1.06 ± 0.03	0.57 ± 0.05	1.04 ± 0.18	0.51 ± 0.03	0.88 ± 0.05	0.59 ± 0.02	1.05 ± 0.05	0.55 ± 0.01	0.93 ± 0.03
20:0	0.34 ± 0.03	0.47 ± 0.03	0.34 ± 0.01	0.49 ± 0.24	0.24 ± 0.02	0.35 ± 0.02	0.38 ± 0.03	0.35 ± 0.02	0.31 ± 0.02	0.31 ± 0.01
20:1	0.29 ± 0.01	0.13 ± 0.03	0.22 ± 0.02	0.24 ± 0.16	0.17 ± 0.01	0.11 ± 0.04	0.19 ± 0.01	0.11 ± 0.04	0.17 ± 0.01	0.13 ± 0.07
22:0	0.09 ± 0.01	0.22 ± 0.03	0.08 ± 0.00	0.31 ± 0.07	0.05 ± 0.01	0.27 ± 0.08	0.10 ± 0.01	0.25 ± 0.03	0.05 ± 0.01	0.25 ± 0.08
Others	-	0.19 ± 0.12	-	0.39 ± 0.35	-	0.13 ± 0.03	-	0.09 ± 0.02	-	0.14 ± 0.05
Total SFA	16.6 ± 0.02	17.9 ± 0.09 a	16.8 ± 0.03	18.8 ± 0.30 a	18.0 ± 0.05	18.6 ± 0.14 a	19.1 ± 0.06	20.1 ± 0.32 b	15.3 ± 0.02	16.6 ± 0.16 c
Total MUFA	63.2 ± 0.10	61.9 ± 0.25 a	76.4 ± 0.23	72.4 ± 1.75 b	77.1 ± 0.27	74.7 ± 0.68 c	65.9 ± 0.30	64.5 ± 1.58 d	81.1 ± 0.10	78.3 ± 1.44 e
Total PUFA	20.24 ± 0.03	19.97 ± 0.21 a	6.79 ± 0.07	8.37 ± 1.34 b	4.80 ± 0.04	6.57 ± 0.48 c	14.90 ± 0.02	15.33 ± 0.32 d	3.61 ± 0.04	5.04 ± 0.58 e
Unsaturated/SFA	5.04 ± 0.05	4.56 ± 0.18	4.96 ± 0.11	4.29 ± 1.13	4.54 ± 0.12	4.38 ± 0.43	4.22 ± 0.13	3.97 ± 0.74	5.54 ± 0.05	5.03 ± 0.72
18:1/18:2	3.17 ± 0.09	3.22 ± 0.27 a	12.13 ± 0.21	9.63 ± 1.87 b	17.38 ± 0.24	12.60 ± 0.83 c	4.48 ± 0.24	4.40 ± 0.78 d	26.09 ± 0.08	18.65 ± 1.56 e

*Data are expressed as area percent and are the mean ± SD from three separate preparations (n=3). Different letters in value of CRLP within a row are different ($p < 0.05$) by two-way ANOVA analysis.

Table 2. Fatty acid composition of THP-1 macrophages incubated with 'Chetoui', 'Buidiego', 'Galega', 'Blanqueta' and 'Picual' CRLP for 24h.

	Control	'Chetoui' CRLP	'Buidiego' CRLP	'Galega' CRLP	'Blanqueta' CRLP	'Picual' CRLP
14:0	0.74 ± 0.38	0.28 ± 0.06	0.10 ± 0.03	0.22 ± 0.22	0.32 ± 0.03	0.17 ± 0.07
14:1 n-5	0.13 ± 0.07	0.31 ± 0.03	1.14 ± 0.31	0.95 ± 1.33	0.06 ± 0.02	0.06 ± 0.03
16:0	25.4 ± 1.89 a	17.3 ± 1.51 b	17.2 ± 0.50 b	19.9 ± 0.96 c	18.6 ± 0.65 b	16.6 ± 0.76 b
16:1 n-9	6.14 ± 0.30 a,d	2.04 ± 0.35 b	7.20 ± 2.49 a,c	4.48 ± 0.17 d	2.59 ± 0.10 b	2.59 ± 0.27 b
16:1 n-7	0.33 ± 0.06	0.35 ± 0.04	0.11 ± 0.02	0.19 ± 0.05	0.28 ± 0.02	0.12 ± 0.01
16:1 n-5	0.51 ± 0.14	0.66 ± 0.00	1.80 ± 0.10	0.34 ± 0.04	0.34 ± 0.07	0.21 ± 0.05
18:0	14.5 ± 0.50 a	7.94 ± 0.37 b,d	7.27 ± 0.18 b	8.58 ± 0.64 b,d	6.69 ± 0.98 b,c	9.55 ± 0.88 d
18:1 n-9	32.0 ± 0.33 a	48.3 ± 1.79 b	51.4 ± 0.86 c	49.9 ± 6.21 b,c	51.5 ± 1.38 c,d	59.3 ± 4.07 d,e
18:2 n-6	3.38 ± 0.38 a	13.3 ± 0.91 b	5.92 ± 1.28 c	6.07 ± 0.89 c	11.6 ± 0.28 b	4.43 ± 0.15 a,c
18:3 n-6	0.44 ± 0.10	0.90 ± 0.15	0.70 ± 0.09	0.52 ± 0.02	0.90 ± 0.01	0.73 ± 0.08
18:3 n-3	1.21 ± 0.11	1.27 ± 0.12	1.20 ± 0.01	0.38 ± 0.13	0.97 ± 0.13	1.24 ± 0.07
20:0	1.58 ± 0.01	0.41 ± 0.06	0.20 ± 0.02	0.45 ± 0.04	0.38 ± 0.00	0.24 ± 0.07
20:1 n-9	0.56 ± 0.07	0.22 ± 0.05	0.09 ± 0.05	0.12 ± 0.03	0.18 ± 0.03	0.11 ± 0.02
20:2 n-6	1.22 ± 0.10	0.53 ± 0.02	1.03 ± 0.13	0.67 ± 0.07	0.50 ± 0.04	0.39 ± 0.05
20:4 n-6	4.63 ± 0.15 a	1.79 ± 0.06 b	1.89 ± 0.06 b	2.52 ± 0.64 b	1.80 ± 0.14 b	1.42 ± 0.23 b
20:5 n-3	1.37 ± 0.19	0.72 ± 0.09	0.40 ± 0.08	0.74 ± 0.05	0.68 ± 0.05	0.46 ± 0.28
22:4 n-6	0.39 ± 0.00	0.47 ± 0.15	0.63 ± 0.06	0.94 ± 0.04	0.61 ± 0.10	0.50 ± 0.08
22:5 n-6	1.21 ± 0.22	0.53 ± 0.18	0.23 ± 0.03	0.85 ± 0.06	0.75 ± 0.04	0.76 ± 0.01
22:5 n-3	1.64 ± 0.31	0.49 ± 0.10	0.36 ± 0.01	0.87 ± 0.10	0.42 ± 0.03	0.40 ± 0.07
22:6 n-3	2.45 ± 0.29	2.16 ± 0.41	1.15 ± 0.58	1.30 ± 0.56	0.81 ± 0.11	0.75 ± 0.09
Total SFA	42.4 ± 0.70 a	26.0 ± 0.50 b	24.7 ± 0.18 b	29.2 ± 0.46 c	26.0 ± 0.42 b	26.5 ± 0.45 b
Total MUFA	39.7 ± 0.16 a	51.8 ± 0.38 b	61.8 ± 0.64 c	56.0 ± 1.31 d	54.9 ± 0.27 d	62.4 ± 0.74 c
Total PUFA	17.9 ± 0.19 a,d	22.2 ± 0.22 b	13.5 ± 0.23 c	14.9 ± 0.26c	19.0 ± 0.09 d	11.1 ± 0.11 e
Unsaturated/SFA	1.36 ± 0.35	2.85 ± 0.36	3.04 ± 0.35	2.43 ± 0.68	2.84 ± 0.26	2.77 ± 0.43
18:1/18:2	9.48 ± 0.35 a	3.62 ± 1.35 b	8.69 ± 1.07 a	8.22 ± 3.55 a	4.44 ± 0.83 b	13.4 ± 2.11 c

Data are expressed as area percent and are the mean ± SD from three separate preparations (n=3). Different letters in values within a row are different ($p < 0.05$) by two-way ANOVA analysis.

Figure 1.

Control

Galega CRLP

Chetoui CRLP

Blanqueta CRLP

Buidiego CRLP

Picual CRLP

Figure 2.

Figure 3.

TOC Graphic

